

The Effect of Age on the outcome of Teenage Pregnancy in Nigeria: A Demographic Study

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ABSTRACT

Teenage childbearing in developing countries has been a thing of great concern as it has often led to a number of socio – economic problems both to the society and to the families affected. The outcome of teenage pregnancy has been generally associated with higher rates of maternal morbidity and mortality, greater risks for delivery complications, low-birth weight, infants and child mortality. As a result of teenagers' physiological and social immaturity and their lack of adequate prenatal care, health risks associated with their pregnancies and childbearing are more pronounced than those of older women. Therefore this study has examined the relationship between the age of teenagers and the outcome of teenage pregnancy. Based on this study, the result of the analysis shows that both teenagers and older mothers suffer similarly during child bearing. Hence improve medical care is paramount in all the situations.

Keyword: *Childbearing, Mortality, Nigeria, Pregnancy, Prematurity, Teenagers,*

INTRODUCTION

Teenage pregnancy is a pregnancy in a young woman who has not reached her 20th birthday. For decade, teenage pregnancies have been issues in both developed and developing countries as 4 out of 10 girls either get pregnant or procure abortion before they reach age of 20 years. Teenage pregnancy is a scourge that is on the increase and more teenagers are being victims of peer pressure and on daily basis. [1] noted that those affected are usually faced with difficult challenges which include dropping out of school, interruption in other important plans concerning their lives, feeling of rejection among the family members etc. The situation in extreme cases could subject them under pressure and lead them to emotional crisis which in turn could result to high blood pressure, premature birth, low birth weight and in some cases death of either mother or baby especially when the reproductive organ are not yet matured. [2] observed in Akungba A koko a village in Ondo State that the majority of the women become mothers while in their teen's. It has been observed that the rate of teenage pregnancy is on the increase mostly in the rural areas. The United Nations says that 53,000 women in Nigeria die annually of pregnancy related illness, but teenage mothers are at high risk because of poverty, lack of access to health care and a culture that does not like to talk about sex. [3] stated that female child bearing matters from many point of view such as demographic, economic and sanitary. He further referred to the cases in Uruguay that teenage pregnancy is responsible for poverty reproduction and worsening of social status and he concluded that poorer and lesser educated families resulted from their reproductive cycle, in the sense that, the younger the mother is as at the time of first child birth, the faster the family growth rate in short time (higher number of children at the same mothers age) the higher

the fertility rate and the earlier the emancipation of the child birth compared with those who postpone motherhood at 21 or more. Viewing teenage pregnancy from an economic point of view, teenage pregnancy could be as a result of a truncation in their educational opportunities as well as of lower future family income; this could have a social and sociological implication that might compromise the life project of teenagers beyond motherhood and sanitary consequences due to its effect on the mother, the child, and the whole family thereby imposing high costs to the society. In Uruguay, abortion were illegal between 1963 and 1996 teenage fertility rate grew 33% for women aged 15- 19 and 66% for aged 10- 14, as it declined for those between 20 and 29 years old. This gave a higher participation of teenagers in the overall fertility rate between 1996 and 2004. Although the teenage fertility rates (15-19) fell by 16 %.The contribution of teenage women remain the same, Varela as cited in [3]. He further noted that, the growth that the teenage fertility rate has experienced over last 50 years is highlighted by demographers as the most important reproductive change being the most responsible for the maintenance of the reproductive levels particularly until the mid nineties. Study carried out by [4] stated that in Zaria Nigeria, maternal mortality among women younger than 16 is nearly six times that of women aged 20- 24. Adedoyin and Adetoro as cited in [4] observed that anemia and hemorrhage also occur more frequently among adolescent women, they states that in Nigeria, about 60% of the teenage mothers were anemic compared to 15% of 500 women aged 24 -30. In most African countries many of the problems associated with child bearing are due to lack of timely and appropriate health care during pregnancy. Khasiani as cited in [5] that more than one third of expectant school age girls received no prenatal care and 28% attended a clinic for the first

time in their eighth or ninth month of pregnancy in a country like Kenya. Some studies shows that infant born to women younger than twenty years of age were more than two times likely to be of low weight than those born at aged 21 to 30 years of age, infant born to teenage mothers have higher rate of mortality and morbidity than those born to older women. The younger the women, the greater the likelihood that mother and child will experience health complications due to late prenatal care, poor nutrition and other factors associated with life style, the offspring of teen mothers are likely to be poor, abused and neglected than those from the older mothers. The study by Annie E Cassey (1998) found that children of teenage mothers are almost three times more likely to be incarcerated during their adolescent or early twenties than the children of older women. The chance of children born to teen mothers becoming teenage parent themselves is higher than the chance in those of the older mothers; as such the former faces more challenges resulting from the effect of teenage pregnancy. They are more at risk of suffering proportionately from reproductive health and pregnancy related problems. The World Health Organization(WHO) [6] has said that Nigeria and six other countries account for half of the worlds adolescent birth and estimated that 16 million girls age between 15 and 19 give birth every year, with percent of this birth occurring in developing countries, this make up 11% of all birth worldwide. Although the circumstances of adolescent pregnancy and child birth vary greatly, younger female bodies are not fully developed to go through the process of pregnancy and child birth without adverse effects. Adolescent mothers face a higher risk of obstructed labour than women in their twenties. In some cases, child bearing can shape or alter the entire life of a woman. From economic point of view, the rate of population growth are more likely to be rapid in a population where women have their first child before they are in their twenties; this is because a large percentage of this young people are more sexually active[7]. The social and economic consequences for an adolescent having a baby sometimes depend on her particular culture, family and community settings; however, the physical health consequences for the mother and her child are more universally viewed as a thing of great concern. From the view point of both society and family, when a very young adolescent become pregnant and give birth, the consequences are even more severe. In society with good nutritional level and wide spread access to high quality nutritional levels and wide spread access to high quality prenatal care, the physical risk of having a child may not be considered significant when the mother is 15-16 years. However, in countries where anemia and malnutrition are common and where access to health care is poor, childbearing among 18-19 years old whose physical growth is incomplete may bring disproportionate health risks. The severity of the social and personal consequences of adolescent childbearing is also likely to be greater. The younger the age at birth a young woman at the level of schooling is, the likely it is for her to be unmarried and as such becomes a burden to her family, in some cases they may not accept her; however, if they eventually accept her and her baby, she may have the opportunities to develop her own identity.

Generally speaking, teenage pregnancy have a strong and unwelcome association with low level of educational achievement for young women which in turn may have a negative impact on their contribution to the society. From the perspective of the teenage herself and of her family, the meaning and consequences or effect of child bearing during the teenage age ranges and varies widely, this consequences varies from the positive (i.e the fulfillment of an unexpected progression from child bearing to the adult status conferred by marriage, motherhood and the joy and reward of having a baby) to the negative (i.e the assumption of the burden of caring for and bringing up a child before the mother is emotionally and physically prepared to do so). In some countries, an unmarried teenage mother is likely to experience social ostracism and financial difficulties. Early child bearing can also mean unhappiness because the birth was unplanned. marital conflict resulting from marrying in order to have a child born within a socially recognized union, disappointment because of failure to complete secondary school or to go beyond it and loss of earning opportunities [8]. Some risks teenage mothers are likely to face, are as follows: Physical health risk which include pregnancy induced hypertension, anemia, pre term delivery, low birth weight; mental health risk and Social risk which include; dropping out of school, poverty, lack of acceptance, support and understanding from the family members, isolation from her peer groups, exposure to domestic abuse and violence, etc [9]. It is on this bases that this study aims at examining the number of teenage child births and the effect of age on the outcome of teenage childbearing.

METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this study, data were collected from the general hospital, in Ondo State of Nigeria for a period of twelve years; 2002-2013. The three major negative outcomes of teenage pregnancy which are identified as stillbirth, premature birth and maternal mortality were considered. The age range considered here as Teenagers are those within the age of 13-19 years who are unmarried. The data are as shown on tables 1 and 2 below

Table 1 Age of Teenager And The Major Outcome Of Teenage Pregnancy

Teenager Age (Y)	Still birth(X_1)	Premature birth (X_2)	Maternal mortality(X_3)
13	53	45	18
14	43	40	21
15	48	46	23
16	41	37	16
17	36	38	19
18	39	50	27
19	39	39	16
20	49	42	19

From table 1 above, it can be clearly seen that still birth was the highest negative outcome with a value of 53 at the age of 13 years, followed by premature birth with the value of 50 at the age of 18 years. Maternal mortality was also observed but not as much as still births and premature births. Considering these outcomes over the years;

Table 2 Outcome Of Teenage Pregnancy Over The Years (2002-2013)

Years(Y)	Still birth (X1)	Premature birth (X2)	Maternal mortality (X3)
2002	31	22	12
2003	28	27	19
2004	28	30	16
2005	25	26	12
2006	35	20	12
2007	25	26	12
2008	24	26	12
2009	29	32	14

2010	29	32	12
2011	40	38	13
2012	24	28	12
2013	30	30	13
Total	348	337	159

From table 2 above, still birth still recorded the highest outcome with a total value of 348 for the period under study, followed by premature births.

To determine the relationship between the age of Teenager and the possible outcome of Teenage pregnancy, regression analysis carried out using table 2 above gave the result as shown below;

Model Summary

Model 1	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. error of the estimate	R ² change	F change	df 1	df 2	Sig.F change
1	.46 ^a	0.210	-0.382	2.87924	0.210	0.355	3	4	0.789

a Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

ANOVA(b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.840	3	2.947	.355	.789(a)
	Residual	33.160	4	8.290		
	Total	42.000	7			

a Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

b Dependent Variable: Y

Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	21.665	11.343		1.910	.129		
	X1	-.257	.257	-.620	-1.000	.374	.513	1.949
	X2	.301	.583	.554	.516	.633	.171	5.850
	X3	-.334	.660	-.507	-.505	.640	.196	5.098

a Dependent Variable: Y

Collinearity Diagnostics(a)

Model	Dimension	Eigenvalue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions				
				(Constant)	X1	X2	X3	(Constant)
1	1	3.967	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	2	.025	12.529	.02	.13	.00	.00	.12
	3	.006	24.722	.84	.35	.00	.00	.03
	4	.001	56.745	.14	.52	1.00	1.00	.85

a Dependent Variable: Y

Model Summary

Model 1	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std. error of the est.	R ² change	F change	df 1	df 2	Sig.F change
1	.46 ^a	.210	-.382	2.8792	0.210	0.355	3	4	0.789

a Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

ANOVA(b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.840	3	2.947	.355	.789(a)
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a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Coefficients(a)

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1	(Con.)	21.665	11.343		1.910	.129		
	X1	-.257	.257	-.620	-1.000	.374	.513	1.949
	X2	.301	.583	.554	.516	.633	.171	5.850
	X3	-.334	.660	-.507	-.505	.640	.196	5.098

a. Dependent Variable: Y

RESULT

The result of the regression analysis carried out using table 1 above gave R^2 value of 0.210 indicating that the variables considered accounted for just 21% of the total variation. This supports the study by [10] showing that both teenagers and older mothers suffer similarly during child bearing irrespective of age.

CONCLUSION

This study has shown that age has much effect on the outcome of teenage pregnancy, as can see on the high number of recorded still births and premature births at the ages of 13 and 18 respectively. However, the result of regression analysis has shown that both teenagers and older mothers face similar challenges during child bearing with just about 21% variation being accounted for, by the variables used. Therefore, one can say that much as teenage pregnancy is not encouraged, emphasis should be on proper medical attention and facilities available to them during child birth and on the socio economic effect it has on them both during the period of pregnancy and after child birth.

REFERENCES

- Denise Witner, "Socio-economic implication of early teenage pregnancy". Richyfvrit Publishing company Liverpool. 2nd Edition on July 2012.
- Olaogun Dunsunmi (2011) "Journal on teenage Childbearing in Ondo state"
- Zuleika ferre ,Mariana Gerstenblüth, Máximo Rossi and Patricia Triunfo (2009). The impact of teenage
- childbearing on educational outcomes. http://www.academia.edu/9621352/The_impact_of_teenage_childbearing_on_educational_outcomes Accessed 3rd March, 2015
- K.A Harrison, and C.E Rossiter, Maternal Mortality: Childbearing, health and social priorities: A survey of 22,777 consecutive hospital births in Zaria, Northern Nigeria. British Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology Supplement 5: 110-115. 1985
- Gebremariam Woldemichael.(N.D) Teenage Childbearing and its Health Consequences on the Mother and Child in Eritrea. Journal of Eritrean Medical Association JEMA. google Accessed 20/09//2014
- [6]World Health Organization (2011) Early marriages, adolescent and young pregnancies. Report by the Secretariat. Executive Board 130th session EB130/12.
- Hofferh and Moore, (1997) "The impact of teenage pregnancy". Hemisphere publishing co-operation, Washington. 1st Edition.
- D Scoth (1991) "Teenage Pregnancy Horror" Dell Publishing Co. Nigeria. 4th Edition
- Oyefara I.J.L (2009) Socio-Economic Consequences of Adolescent Childbearing in Osun State, Nigeria. KASBIT Business Journal, 2(1&2):118 <http://www.kasbit.edu.pk/journal/index.htm>
- Zabin, L. S & Kiragu, K (1998) The health consequences of adolescent sexual and fertility behavior in Sub-Saharan Africa. Studies in Family Planning, 29 (2): 2. <http://www.curationis.org.za/index.php/curationis/article/download/1108/1043>

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